

OPPORTUNITIES OF SPORTS DEVELOPMENT IN DELHI

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Abstract:

This paper tries to provide a trend analysis of sports promotion and development in the past few years. The analysis is based on the aspects of promotion and development of sports only. It has been found that the sport development has seen various aspects further which provide developmental activity through sport. Further, the sports promotion also has been analyzed with the help of available review of literature and it has been found that sports has been promoted through leagues, events and sporting activities which have an upward trend as reported with the higher fan following in the literature.

Keywords: basketball, plyometric, training

1. Introduction

In last two decade, India has emerged as a power in sports. It has become one of the prominent sports nations. In last decade or two, India has successfully hosted some big /mega events. To name few like, ICC Cricket World Cup, World Cup Hockey, Commonwealth Games, Formula 1 Racing, Champions Trophy in Hockey etc. League competitions have been initiated in Cricket, Tennis, Hockey, Badminton, Kabaddi, wrestling etc. Which have emerged as top leagues in world, where top players are participating. In coming years, India is going to host, ICC World Cup T20, FIFA under-17 World Cup etc.

India has emerged a sports nation in terms of participation and winning medals in various games and events. It is now not confined to only few games and events. In last decade or two, it has won medals in shooting, archery, wrestling, weight lifting, judo, athletics, badminton, tennis, golf, etc. apart from cricket.

In the terms of infrastructure, India has been able to produce some big infrastructure like F1 circuit, Stadiums for almost all games and sports. In terms of

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promotion, India has been able to succeed in all games and sports. People are now more aware about games and sports. They are now more aware about fitness and health. Gyms and fitness centers are fast growing business ventures. People from all walks of life are participating in games and sports.

In India, sponsors and media is also playing a significant role in promoting all games and sports. Big industrialists have shown their interest in supporting this great cause. Sports have become one of the most successful industries in the country. Many new sport event management companies have emerged in last two decades.

Now this era, sports plays a very important role for almost every one. Every one try to give time to sports in many ways as actively and even passively. People involved in sports as participants and as viewers. From the beginning of 21st century, sports become developed day by day. We can able to see that numbers of sports participation in various games and events are increasing. People are showing more interest to participate in games & events for recreational and leisure.

India has successfully organized so many events within these years 2000 to 2015. Events in international level, continental level and domestic level. i.e. Common Wealth Game (2010) in International level, Women Asian Cup(2006), Indian Premier league (2015) etc. appendix I, appendix II and appendix III. With the successful organization of all these events, the atmosphere of India towards sports has changed. Job opportunities have been created in sports and people are opting sports as good career. Numbers of sports goods manufacturing units/factories have increased and the demand of goods/equipment has increased not only from the country but from abroad also. With global level events round the year, has attracted many foreign tourists and India has emerged as one of the favorite destinations and has boosted sport tourism.

2. Material and Methods

Most of the studies completed on the sport promotion and development has been conducted across the globe. Sports can be developed and promoted through various activities engaging the sports reviews have shown sport tourism, league, marketing development etc. taken place for the development and promotion of sport.

A study on sport tourism was conducted in Taiwan which reported that event sport tourism (EST) has become an important economic sector around the world EST could also be used as an instrument of city development strategy. In India Smart cities concept is fast being developed which can use the Event Sport Tourism as one of its blocks. (Huei-Wen Lin)

Sport studies are also being conducted by premier India Institution like IIMA. A study was conducted on Sports League which identified the constituents of the sport leagues being successful the study identified fan acceptability as a measure of success of leagues. (Kapoor, 2015)

It has been studied that the sport business industry has a direct influence on entrepreneurship, small, medium and micro enterprises as reported for the country of South Africa. (Mothilall, 2012)

Media coverage has also an upward trend with specific implication to host the sporting events which has been reported in studies making sport a consumer decision-making model. (Getz & Fairley, 2004)

Sport history is analysed in one of the studies. A case of Oman was studied which showed that organised history of sport was not available and also commented that to make sport professionally organised will require various challenges to be overcome. (AL-Busafi, 2012)

Tourists' arrival also is impacted by mega-sports events as reported by one of the studies. Conducts of the sports events are provide lucrative opportunities for tourism. Study has reported that tourism flow toward host countries between 1995-2006 as reported of 200 countries had seen a positive influx of the tourists. (Santana-Gallego, 2011)

Involvement differences exist among gender characteristic and also reveal that individuals' involvement level more significantly impact to recall the sponsors. Study also said that marketer investing more on sponsorship – linked marketing in emerging economics. (Gupta, 2015)

Applying of sponsorship and brand management in global marketing significantly enhance achievement sport business goal and organizational performance in global sport industry. (Rajbhat, 2015)

Sports sponsorship grows hence sporting arena has approaches platform where sponsor become an intricate pillar in the sports industry of Singapore. (Wai)

Sponsorship of Resources and financial support of many companies and stage events relied on event promoter and sport organization. (Zhang, 2015)

Table 1: Research article reviewed and the parameters observed

Sl no	Author year	Parameter
1	Huei-Wen Lin, Huei-Fu-Lu ,2017	Sport Tourism
2	Sanjeev TRipathi and Ankur Kappor, 2015	Sport Market
3	Kush Mothilall , 2012	Sport Opportunities and Trends
4	Getz, Donald and Fairley, Sheranne , 2004	Sports media management
5	Majib AL-Busafi, 2012	Emerging sport nation
6	Johan Fouries and Maria Santana Gallego, 2011	Mega sport event
7	Luke Lunhua Mao and James Zhang, 2015	Sponsorship link market
8	Anish Yousaf and Anil Gupta, 2015	Sponsorship recall
9	Kijpokin Kasemap Suan Sunsndha Rajbhat, 2015	Brand Management
10	Lyon Lai Mun Wai, 2015	Sport Sponsorship

Source: Internet Sources

3. Discussion / Result

The study undertaking on the objectives was comprehensively review on the available literature search. The study show involvement expectation role modelling of parents in

sport as reported by (S. Wuerthe, 2004), (Caokley, 2015) and (Julin E. Bois, 2005). The study shows physical education's impact on sports academic activity as reported by (Richard Bailey, 2007) and (Sheph, 2008). The study show demanding of Sports Goods has been increase as reported by (Andreff, 2009). The study reported the classification of the sports families' temporary local passion devoted fanatical dysfunctional (Kenneth A. Hunt, 1999) (Robert J. Vallerand & Erd. Robert J., 2008) Consumption motives of male were higher than the female reported (Ridinger, 2011). TV sports viewership is related to increased value of advertising increased cross marketing etc as reported by (Donghum & J., 2011), (King, 2010) and (Walter Gantz, 1995). Sports career has been reported differently by authors as play and profession, transition, athlete visa- versa coach relationship in the course of the athletes' sports career. This study has shown sport career as reported (Paul R., 2009), (Taylor, 2010) and (Stambulova, 1999). It is also known that physical education has led to globalization of the gym and fitness culture. The nurturing of the personal trainers, the health and fitness industry resting in customer satisfaction. (Johansson, 2006), (Alain Ferrand, 2010) and (Maguire, 1998). Recreation has always been a major component of the employment and also assisting in recovery. Sports recreation and employment has seen significant relationship for people working at spinal injury centre. As reported by (Nancy A. Murphy, 2008) and (Gardner, 2008). Sports tourism has crossed styles as reported from Canada, USA. It has further intensified and has grown in reorganization as reported by (G., 1991) and (Adair, 2010). Coate and Humphery (2003) have explore the impact of professional sports teams a stadium on employment will have shown a positive relationships (Humphreys, 2003). Sports celebrity has a direct compact on retailing as observed by (Karen E. L., 2009). The role of retailers, especially pharmacist in controlling the menace of doping has been investigates which says 74% can be controlled by them (P. Laure, 2000). Author have reported the enhancement of the sports academies including the changes in the teaming styles utilized 8/29 (Andrew Manley, 2012), (Hou Yulul) and (Dehan, 2010). Infrastructure enhancement has been reported by Matheson (year) in the developing and industrialized countries. (Matheson, 2013). The Olympic Games conducted in a city has a vast legacy impact as studied by (Wilson).

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